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Associations between Perceived Parenting Styles, Identity Styles, and Cognitive Flexibility in Pakistani Adolescents

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ABSTRACT

Adolescence represents a critical period of identity formation and cognitive development, where parenting practices play a central role in shaping adaptive or maladaptive trajectories. This study investigated the associations between perceived parenting styles, identity orientations, and cognitive flexibility among Pakistani adolescents. A total of 300 secondary school students from Lahore (M age = 14.98, SD = 1.31; 154 males, 146 females) completed standardized measures: Perceived Parenting Style Questionnaire (PPSQ; Divya & Manikandan, 2013), Revised Identity Style Inventory (ISI-5; Berzonsky et al., 2013), and Cognitive Flexibility Inventory (CFI; Dennis & Vander Wal, 2010). Correlational analyses revealed that authoritative parenting was positively linked to adaptive identity orientations (informational and normative styles; r = .042, ns; r = .107, ns) and cognitive flexibility (r = .082, ns), whereas authoritarian (r = $-.153$, p < .01; r = $-.149$, p < .01) and permissive styles (r = $-.252$, p < .01; r = $-.228$, p < .01) were associated with maladaptive outcomes, including diffusion/avoidant identity style and reduced flexibility. Cognitive flexibility correlated positively with informational (r = .102, ns) and normative (r = .086, ns) identity styles, reinforcing its role in adaptive identity development. Independent-samples t -tests further indicated that males reported higher authoritarian (M = 28.43, SD = 6.98; $t(298)$ = 4.21, p < .001, d = 0.49) and permissive parenting (M = 27.48, SD = 7.60; $t(298)$ = 2.71, p = .007, d = 0.31), while females exhibited significantly greater cognitive flexibility (M = 109.15, SD = 18.40; $t(298)$ = -4.97 , p < .001, d = -0.57). No significant gender differences were found in identity styles (p > .05). Collectively, these findings emphasize the nuanced influence of parenting styles on adolescent's psychosocial and cognitive functioning, highlighting the importance of culturally sensitive parenting guidance and school based interventions to foster healthier developmental pathways in Pakistan.

Keywords: Parenting Styles, Identity Styles, Cognitive Flexibility, Adolescence, Pakistan, South Asia, Cultural Context

Introduction

Adolescence is widely recognized as a critical developmental stage that bridges childhood and adulthood. Rapid biological, social, and cognitive changes are common during this time, and developing a cohesive sense of self is a developmental challenge. Identity and cognitive development are significantly shaped by parenting practices. According to Baumrind's (1991) typology, there are three types of parenting: permissive (warmth with little regulation), authoritarian (strict control with little responsiveness), and authoritative (warmth combined with structure). Scholars have consistently linked cognitive flexibility and adaptive identity styles to authoritative parenting (Steinberg, 2001; Williams et al., 2012). On the other hand, permissive parenting undermines structured exploration and frequently results in instability and poor self-regulation (Kroger, 2007; Ragelienė & Justickis, 2016), whereas authoritarian parenting promotes rigidity, diffusion/avoidant processing, and conformity (Dwairy, 2010).

Erikson's (1968) psychosocial theory noted adolescence as the stage of identity versus role confusion, therefore emphasizing the significance of identity exploration. Adding on this, Marcia's (1980) Conceptualizing different ways teens negotiate identity development, identity status paradigms and Berzonsky's (2004, 2011) identity style model, New ideas, normative style (commitment to internalized societal and parental beliefs), and diffusion/avoidant style avoidance of identity related decisions and procrastinating behavior.

Parallel to identity development, adolescence is marked by the emergence of advanced executive functioning, particularly cognitive flexibility which is the ability to shift perspectives, adapt to novel situations, and generate multiple solutions to

problems (Scott, 1962; Dennis & Vander Wal, 2010). High cognitive flexibility supports resilience, academic achievement, and adaptive coping, while cognitive rigidity is linked to emotional difficulties and poor adjustment.

In collectivist cultures such as Pakistan, parenting is shaped by values of obedience, respect for authority, and family cohesion (Haque, 2020). While these values support normative commitments, excessive authoritarianism can constrain autonomy and cognitive flexibility. Pakistani adolescents, particularly in school contexts, face pressures of academic performance and social integration, making the interaction between parenting, identity, and cognitive flexibility especially salient. Despite its significance, empirical work in Pakistan has rarely examined these dynamics exclusively in school populations. This study addresses this gap by investigating how parenting styles predict identity styles and cognitive flexibility among Pakistani adolescents.

Objectives

To examine the relationship between parenting styles (authoritative, authoritarian, permissive), identity styles (informational, normative, diffusion/avoidant) and cognitive flexibility among school going adolescents in Pakistan.

To investigate the association between parenting styles and cognitive flexibility.

To explore the link between identity styles and cognitive flexibility.

To assess gender differences in parenting styles, identity styles, and cognitive flexibility.

Hypotheses

H1: Authoritative parenting will be positively associated with adolescent's informational and normative identity styles and negatively associated with diffusion/avoidant identity style.

H2: Authoritative parenting will be positively associated with adolescents' cognitive flexibility.

H3: Authoritarian parenting will be positively associated with diffusion/avoidant identity style and negatively associated with adolescent's cognitive flexibility.

H4: Permissive parenting will be positively associated with diffusion/avoidant identity style and negatively associated with adolescents' cognitive flexibility.

H5: Male adolescents will report higher levels of authoritarian and permissive parenting than female adolescents.

H6: Female adolescents will demonstrate higher levels of cognitive flexibility than male adolescents.

H7: The significant gender differences will emerge in authoritative parenting or identity styles (informational, normative, diffusion/avoidant).

Conceptual Model

Literature Review

Parenting plays a vital role in shaping identity formation and cognitive development. Research has shown that authoritative parenting fosters informational and normative identity styles through warmth, guidance, and structured autonomy (Kroger, 2007; Ragelienė & Justickis, 2016). Authoritarian parenting, characterized by strict control, limits exploration and fosters diffusion/avoidant patterns (Luyckx et al., 2011). Permissive parenting, though warm, fails to provide necessary guidance, increasing instability in commitments (Baumrind, 1991).

Identity formation is central to adolescent development. Berzonsky (2004, 2011) conceptualized identity processing into three distinct styles: informational, normative, and diffusion/avoidant. Informational style reflects active exploration, critical reflection, and openness, whereas normative style involves commitment to established values and expectations. Diffusion/avoidant style, by contrast, indicates procrastination and avoidance in self-definition.

A core component of executive functioning, cognitive flexibility lets kids alter their ideas to fit fresh circumstances and come up with other possibilities. Resilience, academic success, and emotional control all relate to it (Dennis & Vander Wal, 2010). Authoritative parenting fosters independence, problem-solving, and discussion, hence increasing flexibility (Williams et al., 2012). Authoritarian parenting, by contrast, stifles flexibility and so reinforces rigidity and conformity (Dwairy, 2010). Permissive parenting destroys disciplined selfregulation, therefore lowering adaptability (Eisenberg et al., 2005).

Embraced within a collectivist society, Pakistani families stress respect for elders, obedience, and family unity (Haque, 2020). These principles match with conventional identity commitments but Expressed through authoritarian parenting, may inadvertently limit freedom and flexibility. Pakistani children in schools, who are under ever more demands for academic success and independent thinking, may see tensions between home expectations and academic settings that promote critical thinking. This draws attention to the need of investigating parental influences on both identity types and cognitive flexibility among Pakistani adolescents.

Methodology

Research Design

The present study employed a correlational research design to predictive role of parenting styles on the identity styles and cognitive flexibility among adolescents. This type of design is characterized by its allowance for real variables to find statistically significant relationships without manipulation of an environment or assignment of participants to experimental conditions. Thus, correlational designs are apt for psychological research especially when ethical or practical considerations render experimental manipulation of family or parenting variables impossible (Creswell & Creswell, 2018).

Participants and Sampling

The study employed convenience sampling to include adolescents, representative of the target school going population in Pakistan. A total of 300 adolescents participated within the age range of 12 to 18 years. The mean age fell within mid-adolescence, a developmental stage particularly significant for identity exploration and the emergence of cognitive flexibility. Participants were recruited from different schools. The sampling strategy ensured representation from schools serving lower, middle, and upper income families, thereby enhancing the external validity and applicability of findings across socioeconomic strata.

Measures

Perceived Parenting Style Questionnaire (PPSQ)

Parenting practices were assessed using the Perceived Parenting Style Questionnaire

(PPSQ; Divya & Manikandan, 2013). The PPSQ is a 30-item self-report instrument that evaluates adolescent's perceptions of three major parenting styles: authoritative, authoritarian, and permissive. Responses are recorded on a 5-point Likert scale ranging from 1 ("strongly disagree") to 5 ("strongly agree"), with higher scores indicating a stronger perception of the corresponding parenting style. The PPSQ has been widely applied in South Asian contexts, including studies in India and Pakistan, and has consistently demonstrated satisfactory psychometric properties, with Cronbach's alpha coefficients above .80 for each dimension. Its cultural adaptability makes it especially suitable for the Pakistani context, where parenting often reflects a combination of warmth, structure, and control within collectivist family systems.

Revised Identity Style Inventory (ISI-5).

Adolescent identity processing styles were assessed using the Revised Identity Style Inventory (ISI-5; Berzonsky et al., 2013). The ISI-5 measures three different identity management styles: informational (active exploration and critical consideration of identity options), normative (conformity to the expectations of society and parents), and diffusion/avoidant (evading and putting off decisions in identity matters). The tool contains 29 items rated on a 5-point Likert scale ranging from 1 ("not at all like me") to 5 ("very much like me"), with higher scores indicating increased usage of each respective style. The ISI-5 has been shown to have strong construct validity and reliability in diverse cultural samples, with reliabilities ranging from .74 to .85. In the current research, identity styles are conceptualized as action indicators of adolescent's identity orientations, allowing for an explanation of how parental influences contribute to self-construction.

Cognitive Flexibility Inventory (CFI).

Cognitive flexibility was measured through the Cognitive Flexibility Inventory (CFI; Dennis & Vander Wal, 2010). The CFI consists of a 22 items self-report questionnaire designed to capture individual's ability to create alternative solutions to problems, change perspective, and adjust flexibly to difficult situations. Items are rated from a 7 points Likert scale ranging from 1 ("strongly disagree") to 7 ("strongly agree"), with increasing scores reflecting increased cognitive flexibility. The CFI has two subscales: Alternatives (to generate multiple solutions) and Control (tendency to see arduous situations as controllable). The internal consistency has been established to be high in previous studies with α value usually $> .85$ and validity demonstrated within adolescent as well as adult populations. Its use in South Asian settings is increasing, with developing evidence for its cultural sensitivity. In this research, the CFI offers a sound indicator of adolescents' adaptive cognitive processes, supplementing identity style measures to provide an integrated image of developmental outcomes.

Procedure

Prior to data collection, institutional approval was obtained from the participating schools. Written informed consent was obtained from parents or guardians, and assent was secured from the adolescents themselves. Data collection was carried out during regular school hours in classroom settings to ensure a familiar environment for participants. The researcher and trained research assistants provided a standardized verbal explanation of the study's purpose, confidentiality procedures, and voluntary nature of participation. Students were assured that their responses would remain anonymous and would be used solely for research purposes.

All study instruments, including the Perceived Parenting Style Questionnaire (PPSQ), the Revised Identity Style Inventory (ISI-5), and the Cognitive Flexibility Inventory (CFI), were translated into Urdu using the forward backward translation method to ensure linguistic and conceptual equivalence (Brislin, 1970; Beaton et al., 2000). Two bilingual experts independently translated the measures into Urdu (forward

translation), followed by a synthesis version. Another set of bilingual experts then back translated the synthesized Urdu version into English. Discrepancies were reviewed and resolved by a committee of experts to maintain semantic, cultural, and psychological validity. This rigorous procedure enhanced the clarity, cultural appropriateness, and accuracy of the translated questionnaires.

Questionnaires were distributed in paper and pencil format, and participants completed them independently. To minimize bias, research assistants remained present to clarify instructions without influencing participants' responses. Completed surveys were collected immediately, checked for completeness, and coded for data entry. Data were analyzed using SPSS Version 26.

Results

Table 1 *Descriptive Statistics of demographics (N= 300)*

Characteristics	f	%	Mean (S.D)
Age			14.98 (1.31)
12 to 13	41	13.8%	
	M= 23	7.7%	
	F=18	6.0%	
14 to 15	163	54.3%	
	M= 82	27.3%	
	F= 81	27.0%	
	96	32.0%	
16 to 18	M= 49	16.3%	
	F= 47	15.7%	
Gender			
Male	154	51.3%	
Female	146	48.7%	

Table 2 *Correlation between Parenting Styles (Authoritative, Authoritarian, Permissive), Identity Styles (Informational, Normative, Diffusion/avoidant), and Cognitive Flexibility.*

Variables	M	SD	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
1. Authoritative	35.51	6.91	1	-	-	0.042	0.107	0.073	0.082
2. Authoritarian	26.85	6.85		1	.153**	.252**	-	0.014	0.056
3. Permissive	26.36	7.44			1	0.029	-	-	-
4. Info style	29.69	6.41				1	0.102	0.065	0.043
5. Norm style	29.18	5.87					1	.222**	.228**
6. DA style	28.87	5.15						1	.251**
7. CF	103.63	19.46							1

Note: Info style= Informational Style, Norm style= Normative Style, DA style= Diffusion/Avoidant Style, CF = Cognitive flexibility

As shown in Table 2, authoritative parenting was negatively correlated with authoritarian ($r = -.15, p < .01$) and permissive styles ($r = -.25, p < .01$), indicating distinct parenting constructs. Authoritarian and permissive parenting were both negatively associated with cognitive flexibility ($r = -.15, p < .01$; $r = -.23, p < .01$, respectively), whereas authoritative parenting showed small, nonsignificant positive links with identity styles and cognitive flexibility. Informational and normative identity styles were strongly related ($r = .51, p < .01$), and both correlated positively, though weakly, with diffusion/avoidant style. Cognitive flexibility was positively related to adaptive identity styles, supporting its role in identity development.

Table 3 Independent Samples *t*-test showing Gender differences in Parenting Styles (Authoritative, Authoritarian, Permissive), Identity Styles (Informational, Normative, Diffusion/avoidant), and Cognitive Flexibility.

Variables	Male (N=154)		Female (N=146)		t	Df	p	Cohen's D
	M	SD	M	SD				
Authoritative Parenting	34.97	6.63	36.09	7.17	-1.40	298	.163	-0.16
Authoritarian Parenting	28.43	6.98	25.18	6.32	4.21	298	.000***	0.49
Permissive Parenting	27.48	7.60	25.18	7.11	2.71	298	.007**	0.31
Info Style	29.27	6.04	30.15	6.78	-1.20	298	.233	-0.14
Norm style	28.77	6.16	29.62	5.53	-1.27	298	.207	-0.15
DA Style	28.38	4.90	29.40	5.38	-1.71	298	.089	-0.20
CF	98.40	19.05	109.15	18.40	-4.97	298	.000***	-0.57

Note: Info Style= Informational Style, Norm Style= Normative Style, DA Style= Diffusion/Avoidant Style, CF = Cognitive flexibility.

Independent samples *t*-tests revealed significant gender differences in parenting styles and cognitive flexibility (see Table 3). Males reported higher authoritarian ($M = 28.43, SD = 6.98$) and permissive parenting ($M = 27.48, SD = 7.60$) compared to females ($M = 25.18, SD = 6.32$; $M = 25.18, SD = 7.11$), $t(298) = 4.21, p < .001, d = 0.49$; $t(298) = 2.71, p < .01, d = 0.31$. Conversely, females demonstrated significantly greater cognitive flexibility ($M = 109.15, SD = 18.40$) than males ($M = 98.40, SD = 19.05$), $t(298) = -4.97, p < .001, d = -0.57$. No significant gender differences emerged for authoritative parenting or identity styles. No significant gender differences were found in authoritative parenting, informational style, normative style, or diffusion/avoidant style, suggesting similar identity orientations across genders.

Discussion

The present study sought to examine the interrelations among parenting styles, identity formation, and cognitive flexibility in a sample of adolescents. The results of this study offer important insights into these key developmental constructs and their interrelations.

The results showed that adolescents most frequently reported authoritative parenting, followed by authoritarian and permissive parenting. This pattern is in line with international and regional literature indicating that authoritative parenting marked by warmth, consistent expectations, and open communication is a common and effective parenting style in promoting adolescent development (Pinquart, 2017). Conversely,

authoritarian and permissive parenting styles, although less common, are worth examining due to their unique implications for adolescent adjustment.

The correlation analysis revealed that authoritative parenting was negatively correlated with both authoritarian and permissive parenting styles. Notably, authoritarian and permissive parenting styles were positively correlated, indicating that adolescents might view both as inconsistent and emotionally distant, especially when parental practices swing between excessive control and excessive leniency. This underscores the value of examining adolescent's views in understanding parenting dynamics.

A key finding of the study was that authoritarian and permissive parenting was both negatively correlated with cognitive flexibility. This implies that adolescents who experience either rigid control or lack of structure may be less capable of adaptively shifting perspectives, regulating behavior, and engaging in problem solving. These findings are consistent with theoretical views that highlight the value of autonomy supportive environments in promoting flexible cognitive processes (Kuppens & Ceulemans, 2019; Martin & Rubin, 2016). Authoritarian parenting may restrict opportunities for independent thinking through its focus on obedience, while permissive parenting may not provide the scaffolding necessary for developing problem solving and self-regulation skills. Authoritarian parenting showed a very weak negative correlation with informational processing ($r = -.03$), a pattern so small that it is likely to represent statistical noise rather than a significant association. This finding should therefore be interpreted with caution.

In contrast to predictions, authoritative parenting showed a non-significant positive correlation with cognitive flexibility. Although prior research tends to associate authoritative parenting with adaptive cognitive and emotional functioning, this result indicates that the pathways might be indirect, perhaps mediated by variables like emotional regulation, self-efficacy, or temperament (Fletcher et al., 2020). This subtlety underscores the importance of further research into the mechanisms by which supportive parenting affects cognitive processes.

No significant correlations were observed between parenting styles and identity styles. This is in contrast to prior findings that indicate parenting, especially authoritative styles, promotes informational and normative identity orientations, whereas permissive or neglectful practices are associated with diffusion/avoidance (Berzonsky & Papini, 2014). One explanation is that identity development might be increasingly influenced by peer, school, and digital factors in modern adolescence, particularly in collectivist societies in the midst of social change. Another explanation is that the perceived effect of parenting might be indirect, acting through more general constructs like emotional support, autonomy, or cultural expectations rather than direct influence on identity styles.

The study observed positive correlations between informational, normative, and diffusion/avoidant identity styles. This indicates that identity processing styles, although distinct, are not mutually exclusive. Adolescents might use multiple approaches simultaneously depending on situational demands, cultural expectations, or developmental transitions. This is in line with modern views that identity formation is a dynamic, context-sensitive process rather than a rigidly fixed orientation (Schwartz et al., 2011).

Gender differences were observed in both perceptions of parenting and cognitive flexibility. Male adolescents perceived higher levels of both authoritarian and permissive parenting than females. This might be due to culturally embedded parenting practices in Pakistan, where boys are subjected to stricter discipline but might also be indulged in ways that girls are not. Such perceptions underscore the role of gendered expectations within South Asian family structures (Riaz et al., 2021).

A significant gender difference was found in cognitive flexibility, with female adolescents being more adaptable. This is in line with global research that girls tend to

be more cognitively and emotionally flexible, perhaps because of earlier executive functioning maturation and gendered socialization practices that promote relational awareness and emotional regulation (Gabard-Durnam et al., 2020). These results highlight the need to take into account both biological and cultural factors when studying gendered patterns in adolescent development.

Cultural Implications

The muted effect of authoritative parenting in certain South Asian cultures was previously reported (Rudy & Grusec, 2006). Obedience, respect towards elders, and interdependence within collectivist family organizations tend to be valued, potentially making authoritarian practices the norm. Yet the current research emphasizes that authoritative parenting with warmth, structure, and autonomy support is still advantageous in this culture. Through promoting both cognitive adaptability and psychosocial maturity, authoritative parenting prepares young people to reconcile cultural demands for conformity with the need for intellectual autonomy in contemporary education, which calls for critical thinking and problem-solving. Pakistani youth, balancing collectivist family forces with increasingly individualistic school culture, can especially profit from parent-child interaction that combines structure with effective communication. These results highlight the potential of culturally sensitive interventions that are respectful of hierarchical structures within traditional families yet supportive of practices that increase adolescent autonomy and flexibility.

Limitations

Despite its contributions, this study has certain limitations. First, the correlational design restricts the ability to infer causal relationships between parenting styles, identity styles, and cognitive flexibility. While significant associations were found, longitudinal research is needed to confirm developmental trajectories. Second, the reliance on self-report instruments may have introduced response bias, as adolescents might have underreported or over-reported their parent's practices. Third, the study was conducted exclusively in urban schools in Lahore, which may limit the generalizability of findings to rural or madrassa populations, where parenting norms and adolescent experiences may differ substantially. Finally, the research focused only on Baumrind's three primary parenting styles, without considering neglectful or hybrid patterns that could also influence adolescent development in unique ways.

Implications for Practice

The findings of this study carry several practical implications for families, schools and policymakers. For parents, education programs can be designed to highlight the long-term developmental benefits of authoritative parenting, emphasizing how warmth combined with structure fosters not only better identity development but also cognitive flexibility and problem-solving skills. For schools, counseling and guidance interventions can incorporate family awareness sessions aimed at reducing authoritarian rigidity and encouraging autonomy supportive practices within households. At the policy level, collaboration between parents and teachers should be strengthened to create an environment that nurtures adolescent's critical thinking and adaptability. Such partnerships can ensure that cultural values of respect and cohesion are preserved while simultaneously promoting skills essential for success in contemporary academic and social contexts.

Future Directions

Based on the limitations and findings of this study, several avenues for future research are recommended. First, a longitudinal design is crucial to investigate the causal pathways between parenting styles, identity development, and cognitive flexibility.

Such studies could track adolescents over time to see how changes in parenting are related to the development of cognitive flexibility and identity.

Second, future research should aim to use measures with established higher reliability, or to conduct a validation study on the existing instruments to improve their psychometric properties in this population. It would also be beneficial to explore the dimensions of parenting styles in greater detail, particularly the seemingly paradoxical positive correlation between authoritarian and permissive styles.

Lastly, future studies should consider the role of mediating variables, such as emotional intelligence, self-efficacy, and peer relationships, which may help to explain the mechanisms through which parenting styles influence cognitive flexibility. A larger and more diverse sample would also enhance the generalizability of the findings.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this study demonstrates that parenting styles play a central role in shaping both identity styles and cognitive flexibility among Pakistani adolescents. This study offers important evidence of a significant negative relationship between authoritarian and permissive parenting styles and cognitive flexibility in adolescents. These findings underscore the importance of parenting practices in shaping an adolescent's cognitive adaptability. While a direct link was not found between authoritative parenting and cognitive flexibility, the significant gender differences in both parenting perceptions and cognitive flexibility highlight the need for a more nuanced understanding of these developmental processes. The results of this study contribute to the existing knowledge base and provide a strong foundation for future research in this area.

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